

Gold nanoparticles for power retention in electrochemical capacitors with KSCN-based aqueous electrolyte

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ABSTRACT

The paper reports the performance of the electrochemical capacitor operating with a nanoparticle-modified electrolyte. 7 mol L⁻¹ KSCN aqueous solution, known as the electrolyte exhibiting redox activity originating from pseudohalide anion (SCN⁻), has been enriched by gold nanoparticles at nanomolar concentration. The cycle life, specific energy of the device and power retention have been improved. The influence of nanoparticles concentration on the electrochemical capacitor performance has also been verified. All the nanoparticle-modified electrolytes display very high conductivity (~370 mS cm⁻¹); it is confirmed that the high energy density is retained at the whole range of applied current densities: 13.7 Wh kg⁻¹ (at 1 A g⁻¹) and 12.1 Wh kg⁻¹ (at 20 A g⁻¹).

1. Introduction

Continuously growing interest in portable electronics imposes the development of various energy storage devices. Thus, researchers are focused on finding new or alternative solutions to the conventional batteries to provide the technology that can be charged faster, delivers more power, and is characterized by long cycle life. All these features must be developed taking into consideration several safety issues and environment-related aspects [1]. Electrochemical capacitors (ECs) seem to meet these requirements; with their specific functional features, they fill the gap between conventional capacitors and batteries. ECs can be charged and discharged faster than batteries, hence, their power density in this context is tremendous [2–5]. To date, main ECs application is found in the electrical equipment e.g., for memory back-up in pagers or microcomputers (to deliver power for a short period and prevent data loss) and portable devices. ECs accompany the batteries in electric or hybrid vehicles. In contrast to the batteries, ECs can be used at very harsh weather conditions (i.e., extreme temperatures) [3,6–10].

Activated carbons with well-developed surface area are the most popular electrode materials for ECs because of their relatively low price, abundance and eco-friendly character [11]. The electrolytic solution could be aqueous, organic or made of ionic liquid [1,2,12,13]. Undoubtedly, the selection of the electrolyte determines the maximum operating window of the device and the final energy/power performance.

It must be pointed out that two different mechanisms of energy storage in ECs can be distinguished. The first one is purely capacitive – charge is accumulated in the electrical double-layer (EDL), formed at the electrode/electrolyte interface. When the EDL is formed, the interaction and structural organization includes the electrolyte species near the electrode surface [13,14]. The second mechanism exploits fast redox reactions with the electron transfer. With these reactions, definitely more charge can be stored in ECs, and, consequently, higher capacitance can be reached. This phenomenon is called pseudocapacitance [15,16]. The pseudocapacitance might have different origin: i) selected transition metal oxides (RuO₂, MnO₂); ii) conducting polymers and heteroatoms incorporated in carbon materials structure (mostly oxygen and nitrogen); and iii) redox reactions of the electrolyte species [17–19].

Nowadays, it is recommended to introduce eco-friendly materials to novel energy storage devices because of environmental issues. These materials should be easily recyclable and must not contaminate the environment. Due to this fact, aqueous electrolytes are getting more and more popular, despite relatively narrow electrochemical window limited by the theoretical voltage of water decomposition (1.23 V) [20]. The most popular examples of water-based electrolytes used in the past are acidic (1 mol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄) and basic (6 mol L⁻¹ KOH) solutions, but their operating voltage is very low – usually does not exceed 1.0 V [21]. Additionally, their pH induces current collectors corrosion during device operation. Hence, other aqueous solutions were incorporated, based on neutral inorganic salts. Sulphate-based aqueous solutions, like 0.5 mol

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L^{-1} Na_2SO_4 and 1 mol L^{-1} Li_2SO_4 , are very popular as the electrolytes in ECs application. Their maximum voltage window is higher if compared to acidic or alkaline solutions (up to 1.6 V with low-cost stainless steel current collectors and for symmetric systems). The origin of such an overvoltage is still discussed, however, the local pH changes near the electrode surface and hydrogen evolution overpotential are assumed to play an essential role [22,23]. However, voltage values for capacitors operating with aqueous medium are still significantly lower than for ECs operating in organic electrolytes – these devices can operate safely up to 2.7–2.8 V [24]. High operating voltage impacts the specific energy E , as expressed by the formula: $E = 0.5 C \cdot U^2$, where U – the maximum voltage (V), C – cell capacitance [20]. As the electrolyte stability is its non-adjustable feature, one can improve the specific energy by specific capacitance increase. In this context, the implementation of redox active electrolytes seems to be a promising strategy.

In the aqueous medium, water can donate a proton to the redox reactions; quinone/hydroquinone redox couple is here a good example [25]. Unfortunately, an acidic medium required for hydroquinone-based species, diminishes the maximum cell voltage and the energy density. Therefore, a mild and pH-neutral aqueous electrolytes demonstrating redox activity are a good solution to this problem. Alkali metal halides – iodides ($\text{I}^-/\text{I}_2/\text{I}_3^-$) [26,27] and bromides ($\text{Br}^-/\text{Br}_2/\text{Br}_3^-$) [28,29] are widely known inorganic salts used for the redox-active electrolytes formulation. Recently, also pseudohalides emerged as an alternative to iodides and bromides and are represented by the thiocyanate/thiocyanogen ($\text{SCN}^-/(\text{SCN})_2/\text{SCN}_3^-$) and selenocyanate/selenocyanogen ($\text{SeCN}^-/(\text{SeCN})_2$) redox-couples [30,31]. Maximum voltage values of the ECs operating in these electrolytes does not exceed 1.6 V and 1.4 V, respectively.

Interestingly, the performance of iodide- and thiocyanate-based systems equipped with gold current collectors was remarked to be better than on stainless-steel or titanium. The current response was better pronounced and their cyclability appeared to be improved. Although gold current collectors in the research practice sounds reasonable, their implementation in the industry is rather excluded. Thus, another solution for introducing gold (either as catalyst or redox mediator) was sought.

Taking into account the peculiar role of gold in the previously presented reports, the improvement of ECs performance by gold nanoparticles implementation to 7 mol L^{-1} KSCN solution is presented in this work. The reactions between gold and iodide or thiocyanate anions have been described in gold leaching processes and the affinity/synergy between thiocyanate anion and gold is widely confirmed elsewhere [32]. Additionally, the aim was to have non-dissolved metal particles in the electrolytic solution. That is why gold nanoparticles were chosen for ECs performance improvement and - to the best of our knowledge - they have never been used as an additive to the redox-active electrolyte (so far).

2. Experimental

Composite electrodes in the form of pellets were composed of 80 wt % active material (carbon black BP2000 by Cabot and activated carbon YP-50F by Kuraray), a carbon black C65 (10 wt %; SUPER C65 by Timcal), as a conducting agent, and PTFE (10 wt %; Sigma-Aldrich, 60 wt % in water) as a binder. Then, the materials were mixed in ethanol (96% supplied by Avantor). The produced slurry was stirred at elevated temperature until the solvent evaporated. The obtained electrode dough was rolled to form an electrode film of a thickness of 250 μm . After that, the electrodes with a diameter 10 mm were cut and dried under vacuum at 120 °C. In the case of the activated carbon Kuraray YP50-F the electrode mass was $\sim 10 \text{ mg}$ ($\sim 12.7 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$), whereas for activated carbon black the mass was in range 6–8 mg (7.6–10.2 mg cm^{-2}). For the Raman tests, microporous carbon cloth was used (Kynol® 507-20). The porous texture and surface area of electrodes were determined by nitrogen adsorption/desorption at 77 K (ASAP 2460, Micromeritics®). The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) equation was used to estimate the specific

surface area (S_{BET}) of the electrode materials; the pore size distribution (PSD) was calculated by using two-dimensional non-local density functional theory (2D NLDFT) [33]. All the electrochemical measurements were carried out in the two- and three-electrode Teflon Swagelok® cells equipped with the stainless steel (SST) current collectors and, in the case of three-electrode set-up, the reference electrode – Hg/Hg₂SO₄ in 0.5 mol L^{-1} K₂SO₄ solution. The electrodes were separated by a glass fiber filter (GF/D, Whatman: 0.67 mm thickness and pore size 2.7 μm) and soaked in an electrolyte. The tested electrolytes were prepared by dissolution of potassium thiocyanate (ACS Reagent, purchased from Sigma-Aldrich), potassium iodide (ACS Reagent, purchased from Fluka) and lithium sulphate ($\geq 98.0\%$ purchased from Sigma-Aldrich) with appropriate amount of gold nanoparticles (10 nm diameter, stabilized suspension in 0.1 mM phosphate buffered saline (PBS) purchased from Sigma-Aldrich). Conductivity and pH of the electrolytes were measured with Conductometer S230 SevenCompact™ (Mettler Toledo; accuracy $\pm 0.5\%$) and pH meter S220 SevenCompact™ (Mettler Toledo; pH relative accuracy ± 0.002), respectively, at ambient temperature.

Electrochemical investigations were carried out using the multi-channel potentiostat/galvanostat VMP3 (BioLogic, France). The following electrochemical techniques were used: cyclic voltammetry (CV, 10–500 mV s^{-1}), galvanostatic charge/discharge (GCPL, 0.5–20 A g^{-1}) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS, 10 mHz –100 kHz). The specific capacitance values were calculated per active mass of the active material based on the equations presented elsewhere [34], and then recalculated per device. The capacitance of the single electrode was estimated from the CV data (for the voltage range of 1.6 V), based on the curve integration and recalculated for the potential range for each electrode.

The capacitance is expressed for the mass of both electrodes only, as the volume of electrolyte strongly depends on the cell construction. In our case, for lab-scale models, the calculation with electrolyte mass included gives $\sim 1.4 \text{ F g}^{-1}$ (at 1 A g^{-1}) vs. 36 F g^{-1} without considering electrolyte calculated for capacitor voltage of 1.6 V. One should be aware that the electrolyte volume in Swagelok cell is in a great excess (about 0.2 cm^3). Taking into account the pore volume (0.026 $\text{cm}^3/\text{electrode}$ for BP2000 and 0.0064 $\text{cm}^3/\text{electrode}$ for YP-50F) and electrolyte density (1.33 g cm^{-3}) capacitance values expressed per total active mass in Swagelok cell would be highly underestimated, thus we decided to express it for the mass of the electrodes only. Nevertheless, the electrolyte mass should not be neglected and is indicated.

Raman spectra were recorded on a dispersive Raman microscope DXR (ThermoFisher, USA) with 633 nm wavelength laser, 30 s sampling time within the wave numbers of 50–3500 cm^{-1} and laser power 7 mW.

3. Results and discussion

The nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms and PSD, together with respective pore volumes of investigated carbon electrodes are presented in Fig. 1 and Table 1.

It is clearly seen that YP-50F demonstrates typical microporous character, in contrast to BP2000, where the hysteresis loop of adsorption/desorption process at higher relative pressures indicates the presence of mesopores. Microporous YP-50F is composed mostly of micropores smaller than 1 nm, whereas BP2000 has smaller number of micropores but definitely higher number of mesopores (pores between 2 and 50 nm) in different sizes. As already known, for the electrochemical capacitors, the higher specific surface area the better [35] but one should be aware that too small pores, like supermicropores and ultramicropores [36] can be inaccessible for the ions and charge storage might be inefficient. In our case, where the anions responsible for redox activity are large [30], enough mesoporosity volume must be ensured in the electrode material.

Conductivity of non-modified 7 mol L^{-1} KSCN solution and all the nanoparticle-modified electrolytes was measured. As expected, this parameter did not change remarkably when the gold nanoparticles were

Fig. 1. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms (a) and pore size distribution (b) for the electrode materials.

Table 1

Activated carbon YP-50F and carbon black BP2000 characteristics.

	YP-50F	BP2000
Specific surface area, $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	1830	1210
Micropores volume, $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	0.7	0.6
Mesopores volume, $\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	0.1	2.0

added to the thiocyanate solution – both values were about 370 mS cm^{-1} . Interestingly, pH value determined for KSCN electrolyte was 7.14 while for the modified electrolytes – about 7.5. Negligible difference might originate from the nanoparticle stabilizer.

Safe maximum voltage for the cell operating in 7 mol L^{-1} KSCN electrolyte was determined as 1.6 V [30]. The same value was chosen as an optimal one for the system with gold nanoparticle-modified electrolytes. This value was determined based on cyclic voltammetry and galvanostatic charge/discharge tests. First, cyclic voltammograms at different voltages were recorded – from 0.8 V up to 2.0 V (with a gradual shift of 100 mV at 10 mV s^{-1}) (Fig. 2A). A relatively slow scan rate has been selected to observe capacitive response as well as current increase caused by ongoing redox reactions.

Up to 0.9 V voltage, the shape of the CV curve is typical for electrical double-layer charging/discharging. After exceeding this value, reversible peaks attributed to redox activity $2\text{SCN}^-/(\text{SCN})_2(\text{liquid})$ appeared. The current of the peaks progressively increases with increasing vertex voltage. Deterioration of voltammograms is seen above 1.6 V . It means that additional processes are ongoing in the system – most likely electrolyte decomposition and/or carbon surface oxidation – and cause performance deterioration. In the case of system operating in non-modified thiocyanate-based electrolyte the same trend has been observed [30]. It can be thus concluded that the addition of gold nanoparticles to the thiocyanate-based electrolyte does not impact the maximum operating voltage of the device. Despite such a high applied voltage, no sign of corrosion has been observed on stainless steel current collectors. The capacitance values were calculated for each voltage applied and it is seen that the values increase almost linearly with increasing voltage. Noticeably, above the capacitor voltage of 1.6 V the charge/discharge (energetic) efficiency is relatively low and reaches 85% only; the capacitance loss is higher than 20%. These results confirm that 1.6 V is an optimal voltage for the electrochemical capacitor operating in SCN^- -based electrolyte modified with gold nanoparticles.

The next step was to determine the influence of the material porosity

Fig. 2. (A) Voltage widening of the system operating in 7 mol L^{-1} KSCN with 2 nmol L^{-1} gold nanoparticles as additive on mesoporous BP2000 carbon electrodes; (B) capacitance vs. current density of two-electrode cells operating in 7 mol L^{-1} KSCN with 2 nmol L^{-1} gold nanoparticles at microporous (YP-50F) and mesoporous (BP2000) carbons; (C) Capacitance vs. current density for different gold nanoparticle concentrations in KSCN solution. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

on the performance of the electrochemical capacitor. Cyclic voltammograms have been recorded for the cells with different electrode materials (YP-50F and BP2000) at two various scan rates (10 and 200 mV s^{-1} ; Fig. S1). The results (capacitance values from galvanostatic profiles at various current densities) obtained are presented in Fig. 2B.

Different scan rates have been selected to investigate the ability to EDL-formation, faradaic contribution to the charge storage and charge

propagation at different conditions. At 10 mV s^{-1} , rectangular shape of CVs is observed up to 1.2 V , hence EDL is effectively formed. Then, the redox activity of SCN^- appears and the recorded current increases; consequently, the capacity increase is seen at CV curve. It suggests that redox reaction $2\text{SCN}^-/(\text{SCN})_2(\text{liquid})$ does not strongly depend on the material texture. When higher scan rate was applied (200 mV s^{-1}), the current related to the redox contribution is not well pronounced anymore but charge propagation decay is not significant. In this case, the materials porosity seems to affect the redox activity of thiocyanate anions which is more pronounced when mesoporous material (BP2000) is used. For quantitative comparison, the capacitance values calculated based on the galvanostatic technique were correlated (Fig. 2B). In fact, higher capacitance was recorded for the system with BP2000 as electrodes and the capacitance retention at higher loads is better pronounced than for systems with YP-50F. Because of the gold nanoparticles price, the amount of the additive to the electrolyte solution is crucial. Thus, different concentrations of gold-nanoparticles in KSCN solution ($0.1\text{--}4 \text{ nmol L}^{-1}$) have been surveyed. It was done to find the smallest possible quantity bringing benefits to the cell performance. The systems were tested at different conditions – with galvanostatic charge/discharge and cyclic voltammetry techniques. Fig. 2C presents the capacitance vs. applied current density ($0.5 \text{ A g}^{-1} - 20 \text{ A g}^{-1}$). Even at 20 A g^{-1} the capacitance values are quite high – about 29 F g^{-1} for all the cells with AuNPs-modified electrolytes. For the cell operating in the non-modified electrolyte, capacitance is slightly lower – 25 F g^{-1} . The same results were obtained with cyclic voltammetry technique when the cells were charged and discharged with different scan rates applied (not presented here). It suggests that the addition of gold nanoparticles enhance charge propagation and better charge propagation is retained regardless the AuNPs concentration.

Nanoparticles are introduced to the electrolyte solution as a suspension in 0.1 mM PBS (as a stabilizing agent). It is thus necessary to determine the influence of this stabilizer on the electrochemical capacitor performance. The system operating in 7 mol L^{-1} KSCN with PBS addition was charged and discharged with various current densities. The results are compared with non-modified KSCN solution and the electrolyte with AuNPs addition (Fig. S2). Slight increase of capacitance is observed for the system operating in PBS-modified solution in comparison with non-modified KSCN electrolyte. However, still the values recorded for the system with AuNP are the highest ones and the capacitance retention is the highest as well, suggesting improved charge propagation.

To verify whether the presence of gold nanoparticles affects the redox response, two-electrode with the reference experiments, at different voltages (0.8 V and 1.6 V), were performed (Fig. S3). For the capacitor operating at 0.8 V , no redox activity originating from the thiocyanate/thiocyanogen redox couple is seen as both electrodes display symmetric potential profiles. The situation is different at the elevated voltage – 1.6 V . On the galvanostatic charge/discharge profile for the cell (black curve) a plateau is observed when the voltage exceeded 1.1 V and, consequently, the curves recorded for each electrode separately look different. A negative one behaves as a typical EDL-electrode – no redox activity is detected. However, for the positive one, the triangular shape cannot be observed anymore – there is the plateau – denoting the faradaic process. Moreover, the potential range for the positive electrode is narrower than for the negative one. The same trend was observed for non-modified KSCN-based system [30]. It is thus concluded that gold nanoparticles do not impact the operating potential of the electrodes. Efficiency of the faradaic process must be considered as well. It was calculated for both electrodes, based on the curve integration. At the maximum operating voltage, 1.6 V , the energetic efficiency of the positive polarization is 85% , whereas of the negative one – 80% . Although this is not a perfect reversibility, the charge storage process can be considered as an efficient one, keeping in mind the power retained.

The leakage current and self-discharge are significant parameters in

terms of commercial devices – it is crucial to hold a constant voltage with the lowest possible charge and to provide the highest voltage maintenance when the cell is not used. The results of the self-discharge experiment for KSCN-based systems are presented in Fig. 3A.

At first, the maximum voltage was held for 2 h and the leakage current (LC) was measured. In this case, the current needed to hold the maximum voltage was higher when gold nanoparticles were used as an additive to the electrolyte (25 mA g^{-1}) than for the non-modified KSCN-based cell (21 mA g^{-1}). After this time, the cell was left at open circuit conditions and so-called self-discharge (SD) was measured for 6 h . That period was selected because in the case of water-based electrolytes, the SD is very often measured over 6 h , therefore, we decided to follow this convention. Moreover, the most dramatic changes appeared in the initial $4\text{--}6 \text{ h}$. The SD is comparable for both cells as the cells reached about 1 V at the end of the experiment; it gives almost 38% of voltage loss. For comparative purposes, the same experiment was performed for iodide-based systems. In the literature, for NaI-based cells, the voltage drop was about 13% for 0.8 V as the initial voltage [37]; however, the conditions and materials used were different what was the motivation to perform this kind of test at the same conditions for cells operating in 2 mol L^{-1} KI (non-modified and AuNPs-modified aqueous solution). SD was measured for two voltages – 0.8 V and 1.4 V (as a maximum safe voltage reported for this electrolyte), and the voltage loss was calculated as 50 and 64% , respectively (the values were comparable for

Fig. 3. (A) Leakage current measured for 2 h during potentiostatic mode and the voltage drop (at open circuit conditions) in time; self-discharge measured for 6 h ; (B) Cycling results (relative capacitance vs. cycle number) for capacitors with a 7 mol L^{-1} KSCN electrolyte [30] and electrolyte modified with gold nanoparticles. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

non-modified and nanoparticles-modified electrolytes) (Fig. S4a). It can be concluded that in the case of the tested electrolytes, no significant impact of AuNPs on the voltage drop in time is observed. The question is what can happen when gold nanoparticles are added to the solution which exhibits typical capacitive character? Based on the literature [38] and our own studies (Fig. S4b), it was found out that the voltage drop after 6 h at open circuit conditions is about 43 and 50%, respectively. Gold nanoparticles addition impacts SD at both tested voltages. These changes are noticeable – for initial capacitor voltage of 0.8 V, the drop is 24 and 10%, and for 1.6 V it is 50 and 25% for non-modified and AuNPs-modified electrolyte, respectively. The origin of such performance is still under investigation; however, we assume that the presence of nanoparticles impacts the molecule population at the electrode/electrolyte interface and the ion reorganization/redistribution, especially in the vicinity of particle-solvent clusters might be favored.

Cyclability tests were performed to verify whether the presence of nanoparticles prolongs the lifetime of the electrochemical capacitor. The device was charged and discharged repeatedly by galvanostatic/charge discharge technique with 2 A g^{-1} current density. We assumed 20% of initial capacitance loss as the end-of-life criterion. The result of this test is presented in Fig. 3B.

In the case of the device operating in nanoparticle-modified electrolyte this 20% of capacitance loss was achieved after 18 500 cycles. In comparison to non-modified KSCN-based system it is seen that the lifetime of EC was prolonged by 8 500 cycles by gold nanoparticles addition [30].

As mentioned before, specific energy and power of electrochemical capacitors are very important parameters to discuss ECs characteristic. These factors were calculated from constant current discharge profile integration [39]. The Ragone plot (Fig. 4) presents the specific power and specific energy of the tested devices operating in thiocyanate, iodide and sulphate-based electrolytes. These values were calculated based on the maximum operating voltage for each electrolyte (1.6 V for Li_2SO_4 , 1.4 V for KI and 1.6 V for KSCN).

The specific energy of the EC operating in non-modified KSCN solution, at 1 A g^{-1} is slightly higher than for AuNPs-modified one 15.7 and 13.7 Wh kg^{-1} , respectively. When higher values of current densities were applied, the energy is lower in both cases, but this change is more pronounced for non-modified electrolyte (10.8 Wh kg^{-1} vs. 12.1 Wh kg^{-1}).

Considering the data from Fig. 4, the energy is higher for the cells operating in KI as electrolyte than for KSCN-based systems. The same impact of nanoparticles is observed in this case. For Li_2SO_4 as electrolyte

no differences are observed. It means that gold nanoparticles impact the energy and power only for electrochemical capacitors operating in redox-active electrolytes.

To better understand the role of gold nanoparticles during EC operation, additional tests were performed. Theoretically, no influence of gold nanoparticles on EDL formation was visible. However, to prove it, AuNPs were added to a neutral salt solution – $1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Li}_2\text{SO}_4$ aqueous electrolyte. Moreover, to check the kind of the interaction between these particles and redox-active species, AuNPs were added to $1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ KI}$ solution. The iodide-based solution has been chosen for this purpose, as its characteristic is well known and described in the literature.

From the Nyquist plots (Fig. S5 a, c, e) it can be concluded that gold nanoparticles reduce resistance in the cells. This effect is comparable in all cases. However, the electrochemical behavior is not affected by AuNPs addition – the curves are still parallel to the ordinate axis. Capacitance was also calculated from EIS and presented vs. frequency (Fig. S5 c, d, f). EIS was recorded at two voltages – 0 V (full discharge) and 0.8 V (because of different maximum operating voltages of the systems). It is seen that AuNPs do not influence these parameters significantly. However, for neutral Li_2SO_4 and KSCN solutions used as electrolytes the capacitance values are comparable. It is caused by EDL formation only as the capacitance does not depend of the voltage. In the case of KSCN-based system, redox activity is well pronounced at voltages higher than 0.8 V. For iodide-based cells, higher values are reached at 0 V than at 0.8 V, because of the redox activity of iodides in this region [26,27]. Here, it must be reminded that one should be extremely careful with calculating or considering “capacitance” parameter from EIS, as the values might be enormously high, especially at very narrow potential amplitudes and low frequencies but of no practical meaning.

Post-mortem analysis of the electrodes has been performed to describe the mechanisms and the role of the gold nanoparticles in the system (Fig. S6). Firstly, the Raman spectra of pristine material was recorded (black curve). Typical peaks for carbon materials can be seen: G – band (at 1595 cm^{-1}) and D – band (at 1315 cm^{-1}). Next, the positive electrode which had been working in non-modified KSCN-based system was investigated (red curve). D – and G – bands have still been observed; however, their intensity is lower. Additionally, two more peaks appear – first one at 2050 cm^{-1} and second one at 737 cm^{-1} . These peaks are attributed to stretching vibrations of $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ and C–S, respectively [40]. It suggests that the SCN^- anions are adsorbed at the surface of carbon material. The same trend has been observed for the materials that were working in the cell operating in KSCN solution modified by gold nanoparticles as an electrolyte. However, in this case the peaks originating from thiocyanate anions have higher intensity. Surprisingly, no gold nanoparticles have been detected during this analysis. To determine what kind of bonding is created between SCN^- and carbon material the electrode was washed with distilled water and then Raman spectra were collected (blue curve). It is seen that these two peaks related with SCN^- have diminished. Only D – and G – bands have been recorded. Thus, one can conclude that the anions are not chemically bonded with carbon material. Raman spectra have been recorded of the negative electrodes as well, however, no changes in the electrode composition were observed. This suggests that the gold nanoparticles are not covalently (strongly) bound with carbon surface and they rather play the role of the catalyst for SCN^- activity, as no peaks were found after washing. It is thus assumed (and supported by impedance spectra) that the gold nanoparticles are weakly adsorbed at the surface during electrochemical operation and they improve the electrode conductivity, but the energy of interaction is well below the level of typical chemical bond.

4. Conclusions

Carbon black BP2000 is a suitable material for utilization with KSCN based nanoparticle-modified electrolytes for ECs because of its mesoporous characteristics in contrast to typical microporous activated

Fig. 4. Ragone plot comparing the specific power and specific energy of KSCN-, KI- and Li_2SO_4 – based systems (non-modified and gold nanoparticles-modified). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

carbon YP-50F. KSCN with gold nanoparticles has been found as an attractive electrolyte for ECs. Regardless the gold nanoparticles concentration, a significant increase in the performance of the system has been observed. It can be caused by catalytic properties of gold nanoparticles for the redox reaction $2\text{SCN}^-/(\text{SCN})_2(\text{liquid})$. Moreover, the systems can work in wide operational voltage (1.6 V) exceeding the theoretical voltage of water decomposition for time longer than in the systems with 7 mol^{-1} KSCN – based electrochemical capacitor (18 500 cycles). The systems operating in electrolyte with gold nanoparticles allow high specific energy to be reached in mild conditions (comparable values to non-modified electrolyte). At higher current densities, the energy values are higher for the cells with electrolyte modified by gold nanoparticles. Functional groups: $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ and $\text{S}-\text{C}$ derived from the electrolyte have been detected during *post-mortem* analysis at the carbon surface by Raman spectroscopy. The signals were significantly higher when nanoparticle-modified electrolyte was used. However, after washing the electrodes in water, the groups were removed, suggesting that the anions are not chemically bound with carbon material. Also, no traces of gold nanoparticles were observed at the carbon electrode surface after washing, which suggests that gold is also not strongly adsorbed on carbon material. However, presence of the gold nanoparticles improves the electrode conductivity and impacts the power of the cell as well as the redox activity of SCN^- .

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powera.2022.100087>.

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